

THE IMPORTANCE OF INTERDISCIPLINARITY IN UNDERSTANDING AND COMPREHENDING TEXT

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Abstract. *This article highlights the importance of interdisciplinarity in understanding and comprehending the text, improving the processes of working with the text through hermeneutic teachings, focusing on the general and specific aspects of teaching in the study of each discipline.*

Keywords: *text, module, modern system, field of education, didactics, criterion, innovative technology.*

It should be said that since the first years of independence in our country, attention to the field of education has increased. Based on advanced world experience, priority is given to the field of education and training in order to fundamentally renew our lives, to understand the phenomena of existence, and all the forces and opportunities are being mobilized in this way. Serious measures have been taken to maintain positive results in the field of education and overcome difficulties, and relevant measures are being implemented. However, it should be said that today there are still a number of problems that hinder the improvement of the quality of education in higher education institutions, the wide-ranging reforms implemented in the republic, and the active participation of these institutions in social and economic reforms, in particular : firstly, the system of evaluating the knowledge of students studying in the higher education system does not meet today's requirements; secondly, the problem of developing the professional competence of professors and teachers, the lack of a modern system for evaluating their knowledge and pedagogical skills; thirdly, the attitude of philology students to grammar and its teaching is not fully formed, there is no hermeneutic concept in understanding the text, it is not possible to determine the ability to think logically in this regard; fourthly, the fact that higher education institutions are not fully equipped with innovative ideas and technological tools, as well as the lack of a sense of initiative, remains a problem. For this purpose, the fundamental improvement of the quality of education of students of higher education institutions, in particular, the Faculty of Philology, ensuring their active participation in the comprehensive reforms implemented in the country, the development of their knowledge, skills and abilities in the field, five priority areas fulfillment of the tasks defined in the Action Strategy is one of the most urgent issues of today. For this purpose, the application of the module system of teaching in higher education institutions is one of the urgent tasks on the agenda. In the theory of modular teaching, the main concept is a module. What is the module itself and when and by whom was it first introduced into the educational system? The concept of a module was first proposed by the American scientist D. Russell in the 70s of the 20th century. According to the American scientist D. Russell, the module is a separate part of the educational materials. So, the module can consist of several educational modules. Each of these modules represents a completed process. The expansion of the educational modules and the introduction of additions to them will further improve the content of the module. The introduction of modular training in the educational system helps to increase the efficiency of training qualified personnel. The effect of the innovation introduced into any system can be effective only if it is carefully adopted by its

participants. For this, the study of best practices, discussion on the basis of seminars and trainings, and the implementation of organizational measures will allow to apply modern forms and methods of modular teaching to the educational process. In order to achieve the expected result, it is important to modernize education, in particular, to organize mother tongue teaching on the basis of innovative technologies. In order to implement innovative reforms in the field of education, consideration of objective and subjective needs, motivation to acquire knowledge due to need serves as an extremely important factor. To meet these needs, close cooperation with the world's leading scientific and educational institutions at the level of international educational standards, further development and improvement of the training of real philological experts with higher education, expansion of international cooperation in the field of higher education, improvement of the educational process. The introduction of foreign experiences is the demand of the times. Advancing the purposeful use of language in the context of globalization is one of the main issues. It is known that the use of language tools in various ways in world politics is increasing more and more. But "the Uzbek language, one of the oldest and richest languages in the world, is appreciated for our people as a symbol of our national identity and independent statehood, human consciousness, priceless spiritual wealth, great value" [1].

Today, the language is strongly promoted in ideological landfills. tool, has become a sharp ideological weapon, and through it there is an uncompromising struggle for the possession of human consciousness all over the world. Life shows that weak-willed, shallow-minded people, whose sense of pride in belonging to a certain nation and using its language is fading, and whose hearts are deaf, are becoming untimely victims of this struggle. The most correct way to withstand and win this ideological struggle is to strengthen the faith of the people, to raise their feelings of national pride and national pride. Mother tongue is the main support and driving force of society in such an honorable and urgent work. Because language, as a unique and never-fading mirror of the nation's spirit, reflects the spirit and spirit of this nation in all times. One of the defenders of our language, Abdurauf Fitrat, speaking about the development of the language, emphasizes the following: "Kasrati kalimat (plurality of words)", "Wus'ati Fitrat itself has 98 forms of the word "bil" brought What is most important is proper compliance with language laws and regulations. Fitrat calls it "Joseph perfection". Yusup (Yusuf) is a symbol of beauty, perfection, perfection. Its opposite is "incompetence". It is appropriate to discuss and discuss these methods in order to create love for the mother tongue and its teaching.

In order to positively solve the problems, it is necessary to strengthen the connection of the science "Methodology of mother tongue teaching" with didactics, psychology, and philosophy. We know that linguistics reveals one or another aspect of a language sign (word) and text (thought, sentence) of a certain section. Our subject "Methodology of Mother Tongue Teaching" teaches and is based on the sources and principles of this linguistics. "Within the scope of general linguistics, the nature and essence of language, language and thinking, language and speech, the structural structure of language, understanding the language system, the emergence and development of language, the emergence of writing, morphological (typological) and genealogical classification of languages, languages problems such as the method of scientific study, form and content in language are studied. These are related to language and speech, the method of language testing, problems of form and content in language. In the introduction to linguistics, which is considered a component of general linguistics, basic information about language is provided, the main scientific terms and concepts used in linguistics are introduced, general linguistics is a part

of linguistics and other social sciences (literature, philosophy, history, archeology, ethnology, psychology) and also studies the connection with natural sciences, especially biology and mathematics "To date, the science of language methodology has been studied on a large scale, and has acquired its own research object, studied language units, components, and independent status. With the transition from the theoretical stage of knowledge to the practical stage, it began to have a wider scope. During these years, as in all subjects, the methodology of language teaching has gone through certain stages, the next period was created and developed on the ground of the previous period. Of course, language is a great gift given only to man, which can only be imagined with thought.

The reason why the human factor is the leader in the language is a derivative of the axiomatic view formed on the basis of the fact that the human factor is the only, primary and priority in existence. The manifestation of human emotions is considered an object of study in such fields as psychology, psycholinguistics, and cognitive linguistics.

The methodological basis of the research is based on its purpose and task, along with the analysis of language units, how to use it, and methods of understanding in the process of communication. It is known that it is important to pay attention to the general and specific aspects of education in the study of each subject. General didactics, which is necessary for all educational subjects, determines the activity of the teacher and the student, studies their interaction. "Methodology of teaching the mother tongue" determines the process of how the laws, principles, content, methods, tools, and organizational forms of the educational goal in general didactics occur in the process of teaching the mother tongue. The science "Methodology of mother tongue teaching" is related to the science of psychology and physiology. It is important to take into account the age and individual characteristics of the student in teaching. According to Farabi, we feel *oraz* with the help of our five senses. In particular, speech through the organ of vision; through the hearing organ; taste - through the sense of taste, the state of objects: cold-hotness, hard-softness is felt through the sense of the body, smell through the sense of smell. These sensory organs are also present in non-human animals. Therefore, the above sense organs are common to all creatures. Through them, any living thing practically knows the surrounding world and adapts to it. The knowledge created by a person with the help of sensory organs is considered emotional or practical knowledge. In addition to these, a person can acquire knowledge with the help of imagination and speech. This way of knowing is called powerful speech and powerful imagination. The speaker's power is the leader of all other powers (senses) [2; p. 151]. Sensory knowledge is considered the basis of knowledge and is formed by seeing, touching, hearing, tasting and smelling each thing separately. Although the views of a person are related to a certain subject, it acquires sociality by generalizing with the views of another person, and relations are determined in the process of communication. In the concept of personality, sociality and individuality, generality and particularity, naturalness and artificiality, objectivity and subjectivity are dialectically connected [3]. Therefore, it is important to consider these aspects in order to understand it and to communicate. When talking about the concept of person in linguistics, it should be said that a person is considered the creator and executor of language. He can convey his opinion to the listener in any way and form he wants, and he is also responsible for the reception (interpretation) of this information by the addressee. It depends on the level of communication readiness of communicants. All the means and situations included in the communicative act (speech and non-speech means, situation, socio-linguistic characteristics and mutual relations of communicants,

etc.) are analyzed pragma linguistically and express meaning. [4] Remembering the knowledge and skills acquired from the language, imagining, thinking and being able to use them in speech, summarizing, comparing and drawing conclusions about the events in the language, taking into account the formation of the student as a person gives the expected result. The development of memory, which is related to the mental activity of the person, is important in language teaching. There are five ways to develop memory: the first relies on individual mental properties such as retention, (abstract information) thinking, imagination. Therefore, the teacher should know the personal psychological characteristics of the students and work based on it. Sight, hearing (tone of speech: low, high...), the third factor: smell (opened bread.., or the smell of the earth when it rains, the smell of lemons... although there is no such thing sense of taste (the taste of food...soup, juice...we imagine it even though it is not there...), the fifth factor: touch and see (something hot, or ice... . this is also through imagination), things that give emotion (funny, sad.. animating in imagination). When these six factors are used, there will be an increase in the quality of information that will be remembered. A large volume of data is not remembered. Remember the planets in the solar system; recall using the story method. Can't you see the person on the stage? You want to see. I see Mercury. She is a singer Yulduz Usmonova. What song? At that moment, light falls from the sky. A girl in a white dress comes down to the stand. That girl's name is Venus. He got down and shot the ball in his hand. He flew up and down. Through what sounds it fell to Earth. The dust has risen. The third planet is the earth. At that moment, your neighbor came in, Mars chocolate in his hand. Feel the taste of Mars. To develop memory, you need to concentrate. Ways to improve memory: replay the day, after you sleep.

Reading is not the power of knowledge itself, it is necessary to make efforts to turn it into power. Mind does not play the main role, but action does. It is not enough to know; it is necessary to do it. A blessing in motion. Move.. move.. move..

10 ways to improve memory: 1) eat right, when the body is full, the human brain weakens and it accumulates around the stomach; 2) allow your brain to rest. Rest of the brain depends on sleep; 3) put the mobile phone 1.5 meters away every night. It should not be close to the head. The brain needs to rest. It is advisable to establish a reading routine, neither hunger nor satiety is possible. Sleep comes on a full stomach. Rest 45 minutes a day. Get fresh air; 4) pay attention to every little thing. Remember the small details. Analyze and remember your daily self; 5) make a small map in your mind. Remembering from a book or textbook. Create a map; 6) healthy lifestyle. Practicing mental and physical work. Drinking, smoking is harmful; 7) make a small game with friends. Play various games, word games with friends...enhance your memory with the help of the environment; 8) introduce the necessary information to your brain. repetition, remembering the importance of some; 9) protect the environment. Be with a person who is hungry for knowledge; 10) Never deceive yourself, work on yourself. As Professor D. Orinboyeva noted, Academician Pavlov's doctrine of association (communication, connection) occupies an important place in mother tongue education. If language is not based on the relationship between phenomena, the student cannot perceive the language as a whole system. From a psychological point of view, the knowledge of a person's native language gives him the opportunity to develop it. Communication with the surrounding people, oral and written texts created during the lesson, questions and answers are the factors that ensure development. In a communication situation, a person communicates with other people by means of language, gestures, facial expressions, hand movements, and certain symbolic signs. Choosing the right one from these tools is the task of both

the science of "Psychology" and the science of "Mother Language Teaching Methodology" [5; p. 23]. Both "General Linguistics" and "Methodology of Mother Tongue Teaching" are scientific-theoretical, philosophical, sociological, psychological, methodical, pedagogical disciplines, which train philological students (bachelor's and master's degrees), scientific - is to increase theoretical knowledge. A student will master language teaching only if he knows these theoretical issues. Only then can they draw scientific conclusions and ideas from the analysis of linguistic phenomena, pay attention to the essence of phenomena, and take theory and practice in a dialectical connection. In the process of studying language and speech and a number of issues related to them, he thinks and makes observations based on a number of categories of dialectical philosophy, such as form and content, generality and specificity, essence and phenomenon, cause and effect, possibility and reality. The science of linguistics interacts and cooperates with a number of disciplines. Therefore, it is important to learn the mother tongue and solve issues such as language and society, language and history, language and thought, language and speech. The science of linguistics serves to confirm and prove that language is one of the most important, basic, and unparalleled criteria for the development and prosperity of society. It also helps the learner to develop creative thinking by conveying to the learner the possibilities of the native language - the ways of expressing the same idea, thing and phenomenon in hundreds of ways, the uniqueness of thinking in the native language and the construction of the native language, fundamentally different from other languages: by inculcating reflection of the world "in its own way", it serves as a solid foundation in the formation of national consciousness, national outlook, national pride and ideology [6]. It is desirable to organize dialectics of language and speech based on hermeneutic principles. Sociality and individuality in studying the text is a necessary issue. Because the language belongs to a certain person, learning and understanding it is of particular importance. Be it oral or written, the speech in the text and the understanding of the speech form the basis of speech activity. And on the basis of these, communicative competence is realized. As each student uses the rules of the language, he serves his development. This process is mostly done through texts. V. von Humboldt proves that the language is in constant progress, development, and change, and describes the changes, progress, and development in it directly, absolutely rightly, in connection with society. So, in understanding the text, the history, culture, spirituality of each nation, in general, its entire spiritual and spiritual world is studied. Therefore, it is appropriate to organize the hermeneutic teaching in the interdisciplinary connection in the study of the methodology of teaching the mother tongue in higher education.

Considering that language - social speech - is individual, it is correct to study the attitude of each student to language from a hermeneutic point of view. It is known that dialectical philosophy has its own categories, and it is the only methodological basis in the process of knowing objective reality. Accordingly, the science of the mother tongue is also subject to these categories, receives strength from it, and is based on it. This ensures the objectivity of everything in knowing and studying the world. Because the dialectical categories represent subjects, things, events and processes in nature and their relationship. Our educational system also works on the basis of these laws. Hermeneutics is necessary to understand the content of all spiritual and material values created by mankind, to reveal the content of the worldview of the creator of the work. Through this, the texts are interpreted, through which the spirit of the time is understood, and a general picture of history is created. Therefore, hermeneutics is history, this period, this spiritual heritage. Commenting on the hermeneutic doctrine, we must not forget that it is a practice: "Hermeneutics

is a practice. Anyone who does not draw conclusions from practice and its scale and philosophical origin, despite considering methods based on knowledge gained through thinking, cannot learn the science of applying knowledge with their help. The fundamental truth of hermeneutics is as follows: truth is not defined or conveyed by any individual. To explain one's thoughts at the level of possibility, to learn to express one's being in words is the basis of hermeneutics" [7; p. 69]. So, the task of hermeneutics is the ability to apply theoretical knowledge acquired from the perspective of language methodology in life, to be able to express it through words. We know that the science of language is directly related to logic. Because correct understanding, rational understanding, and mutual compatibility of logical and hermeneutic analysis are purposeful. Hermeneutics is of great importance in understanding logical texts. Therefore, logic and hermeneutics are inextricably linked to each other, because the ability to understand is perfected thanks to logic. Every student can understand through logical thinking, and our relationship to events, phenomena - processes in the world is realized through our logical thinking. Commenting on interdisciplinarity, it is necessary to emphasize that the hermeneutic approach is the basis of philosophy. Now it's time to restore the methodology and use it appropriately, using the legacy of our ancestors, which made it possible to make great discoveries. For a hermeneutic approach to the study of the text, it is necessary to study the methodology used by Abu Nasr Farabi, Ibn Sina, Abu Rayhan Beruni, to know its philosophical foundations, and to use it creatively. Their common aspects are as follows: 1) a substantial (genial) approach to the object. Taking into account the dialectic of generality-particularity, essence-event, possibility-reality; 2) to reveal the conflicting nature of the object. To show that any research object consists of internal conflicts, that these conflicts are the basis of the continuous development of the object; highlighting the systemic nature of the object. To do this, it is necessary to show that each object is an integral part of a certain big whole and, at the same time, it is a whole formed by the interaction of certain internal elements; 4) taking into account the didactics of form and content. Illuminating their interaction; 5) it is necessary to elucidate the types of relations between elements of equal value and between different units (whole and fragment, type and genus). is the process of transforming the thought hidden behind the text into an extended system. It is important for a text perceiver to learn and remember the meaning hidden in the text, based on the actions involved in the text.

The following will make it easier to remember the studied text: pay close attention to it; understand its importance and significance; comprehension and comprehension of the text; distinguishing main ideas or key words; organize and compile information; to know the methods of text grouping and content processing. Memorization is directed to long-term or short-term memorization, depending on the attitude to the material and the level of activity of thinking about the text. There are several ways to remember well:

- dividing the text into groups depending on its content (content, complex, etc.);
- remembering the main points and extracting key words;
- making a plan based on the main ideas;
- forming the structure of the text - dividing it into parts, groups and memorizing the words in it according to their location;
- taking into account and describing the connections between its parts of the text (in the form of a diagram, picture, etc.);
- to imagine information in the form of certain forms and images.

It is necessary to understand and listen to the text in order to remember it well and not to forget it. That is why it is said among the people that "studying is one thing, sleeping is another." It is also necessary to properly organize the repetition of the material. It is necessary to repeat often in the first days after studying. Because these days you can quickly forget what you read. Therefore, it is necessary to study the material regularly, repeat it from time to time during the semester, and memorize it little by little. After all, it is said among the people that "by learning little by little, one becomes wise, and by collecting little by little, one becomes a river."

Also, creating recall words and keys for memory searches during text creation can greatly help in facilitating the retrieval of read material. A student asks himself "why", "when" and "how" questions, making it easier to restore information in memory. The best way to develop your memory is to create your own keywords to make it easier to remember when learning something. In this case, the text is easily remembered with the help of the keys that were used during its study and recall. It is also important to identify cause-and-effect relationships and compare received information with what others know. Thus, the development of memory is often based on the use of key words in the text. Because keywords help to determine the location of the necessary information in the memory. They allow the student to use what he already knows. The ability to find a way to the knowledge stored in memory indicates a person's high intelligence.

Summarizing and concluding the stated opinions, the quality and effectiveness of hermeneutic approach implementation and text creation largely depends on its correct organization and methodological support

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